

EXPERIMENTS ON THE SYNTHESIS OF CYTISINE. PART I.
 SYNTHESIS OF ETHYL 3 : 5-DICARBETHOXYPYRONE-6-
 ACETATE AND THE CORRESPONDING
 PYRIDONES.

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The synthesis of ethyl 3 : 5-dicarbethoxypyryrone-6-acetate has been effected. It has been condensed with ammonia and primary amines giving rise to corresponding pyridones. In course of formation of pyridones, one of the carbethoxy groups in the β -position of the nitrogen atom is hydrolysed and the ammonium form of the pyridone results. β -Aminopropionic ester does not condense with the above mentioned pyryrone. On the other hand, ethyl 3-cyano-5-carbethoxypyryrone-6-acetate condenses with β -aminopropionic ester. The resulting product furnishes a hydroxymethylene derivative with ethyl formate.

The alkaloid cytisine occurring in the seeds of *Cytisus Laburnum* and a large number of leguminosæ was first isolated in a pure state by Husemann and Marme (*Edin. Med. J.*, 1862, 7, 908, 1025) and a considerable amount of work has been done by Partheil* and Freund† and his collaborators regarding its constitution. The present investigation was undertaken to synthesise cytisine which has been assigned structure (I).‡

The fundamental idea underlying the attempt is to effect a synthesis of the pyridone ring A with substituents at the positions '1' and '6' and then to form the rings B and C. For the synthesis of the desired pyridone, the corresponding pyryrone (II) was obtained by condensing sodio acetone dicarboxylic ester with ethoxymethylene malonic ester ($X=X'=\text{CO}_2\text{Et}$; cf. Simonsen, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1908, 93, 1022).

(I)

(II)

* *Arch. Pharm.*, 1892, 230, 448; 1894, 239, 167; *Ber.*, 1890, 23, 3202; 1891, 24, 635.

† *Ber.*, 1901, 34, 605; 1904, 37, 16; 1906, 39, 814; *Arch. Pharm.*, 1918, 256, 33; Ewins, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1913, 103, 97.

‡ Späth, *Monatsh.*, 1919, 50, 1593; *Ber.*, 1932, 65B, 1526; *Ber.*, 1933, 66B, 1338; *Ber.*, 1938, 71, 721. Ing, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1932, 2778; 1933, 504; 1937, 2195.

(III)

(IV)

(V)

(VI)

The pyrone readily furnished the pyridone (III, $X = X' = \text{CO}_2\text{Et}$; $R' = \text{H}$; $R = \text{H}$ or alkyl) in conformity with the observations of Simonsen (*loc. cit.*). For obvious reasons the pyridone (ammonium form) could not be esterified by usual processes. The isomeric ether III, $X = X' = \text{CO}_2\text{Et}$, $R = \text{H}$ or any group; $R' = \text{alkyl}$) could, however, be isolated by the silver oxide method (Irvine, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1908, 99, 1608). Attempted synthesis of pyridone (III, $R' = \text{H}$; $R = \text{CH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{CO}_2\text{Et}$; $X, X' = \text{CO}_2\text{Et}$) from the interaction of pyridone (III, $R' = \text{H}$; $X = X' = \text{CO}_2\text{Et}$) and β -chloropropionic ester failed. β -Aminopropionic ester could not be condensed with the same pyrone. The latter, however, was condensed with β -aminoethyl alcohol furnishing the pyridone (III, $X = X' = \text{CO}_2\text{Et}$; $R' = \text{H}$; $R = \text{CH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{OH}$). The chloro compound (III, X and $X' = \text{CO}_2\text{Et}$; $R' = \text{H}$; $R = \text{CH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{Cl}$) was isolated by the action of thionyl chloride on the above pyridone. It is important to mention in this connection that the hydroxyl group attached to the nitrogen atom of the pyridone in the ammonium form did not take part in chlorination, since under similar conditions chloropyridone (III, $R = \text{H}$; OR' replaced by Cl ; $X = X' = \text{CO}_2\text{Et}$) could not be isolated. The cyano compound (III, $X = X' = \text{CO}_2\text{Et}$; $R' = \text{H}$; $R = \text{CH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{CN}$) could not be isolated by the action of potassium cyanide on the chloro compound. The synthesis of the same cyano compound from the corresponding bromo compound could not also be effected; the reaction with potassium cyanide furnished the pyridone (III, $X = X' = \text{CO}_2\text{Et}$; $R' = \text{CH:CH}_2$). Considering the poor yield of the pyrone (II, $X = X' = \text{CO}_2\text{Et}$) it was thought desirable to replace ethoxymethylene malonic ester with ethoxymethylene

cianoacetic ester. The condensation, however, instead of following the line suggested by Simonsen, gave rise to the cyanopyrone (II, $X=CN$; $X'=CO_2Et$). This compound furnished the pyridone (III, $X=CN$; $X'=CO_2Et$; $R=R'=H$). The pyridone thus obtained could also be alkylated by the silver oxide method. The action of methylamine on this cyanopyrone is noteworthy. In equivalent proportions, it furnished the cyanopyridone (III, $R=Me$; $R'=H$; $X=CN$; $X'=CO_2Et$), but in excess it gave rise to an amide (III, $X=CN$; $X'=CONHMe$; $R=Me$; $R'=H$). The ethyl ether of the amide on condensation with ethyl formate furnished a compound giving colouration with $FeCl_3$, characteristic to β -ketonic esters, probably the hydroxymethylene compound (IV, $X=CN$; $X'=CO'NHMe$; $R'=Et$), thus proving the presence of a methylene group attached to the position 6 of the pyridone ring and consequently of the pyrone (II). β -Aminopropionic ester, however, condensed with the cyanopyrone giving rise to the desired pyridone (V), the ethyl ether of which was condensed with ethyl formate. The resulting hydroxymethylene compound (VI) could not be converted by *cyclo*-dehydration to (VII) with phosphorus pentoxide in ether suspension. The work, however, is in progress.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Ethyl 3:5-Dicarbethoxy- α -pyrone-6-acetate (II, $X=X'=CO_2Et$).—Ethyl acetonedicarboxylate (10 g.) was added to a cooled solution of alcohol (50 c. c.) containing sodium (2 g.). Ethoxymethylene malonic ester (10 g.) dissolved in alcohol (25 c. c.) was added to the mixture. The mixture was then left for 2 hours at 0° , diluted with excess of water and extracted with ether. The aqueous layer was acidified and extracted with benzene. The oil obtained on removal of benzene was heated to $160^\circ/12$ mm., till no more could be distilled off. The residue furnished light yellow plates from alcohol or acetic acid, m. p. 106° . (Found: C, 55.0; H, 5.3. $C_{15}H_{18}O_6$ requires C, 55.2; H, 5.5 per cent).

Ethyl 2-Keto-3-carbethoxy-5-carboxy-1:2-dihydropyridine-6-acetate (III, $X=X'=CO_2Et$; $R=R'=H$).—The pyrone (II, $X=X'=CO_2Et$; 1g.) was treated with aqueous ammonia (4 c.c. of 26%) and left at the room temperature (15°). After 6 hours the mixture was diluted with water to three times the original volume and acidified. The precipitated material on washing with alcohol furnished colourless needles from acetic acid, m. p. 223° . (Found: N, 4.9. $C_{13}H_{15}O_7N$ requires N, 4.7 per cent).

The pyridine when freshly prepared could be dissolved in a solution of

sodium bicarbonate with evolution of carbon dioxide but on keeping for sometime it did not dissolve unless boiled with a solution of caustic soda. Obviously, the freshly precipitated material was the pyridone carboxylic acid which on keeping quickly passed on to the ammonium form. It gives rose-red colouration with ferric chloride.

Ethyl 1-(β)-Hydroxyethyl-2-keto-3-carbethoxy-5-carboxy-1:2-dihydro-pyridine-6-acetate (III, R=X; X'=CO₂Et; R=CH₂·CH₂OH; R'=H).—The pyrone (2.5 g.) in ethyl alcohol (40 c.c.) was mixed with β-hydroxyethylamine (1 c.c.). The mixture was boiled under reflux (5 hours) till colourless flakes of β-hydroxyethylammonium salt of the desired pyridone-carboxylic acid, m. p. 189°, separated. (Found: N, 7.0. C₁₇H₂₆O₉N₂ requires N, 6.96 per cent).

It was dissolved in minimum quantity of water and acidified with dilute hydrochloric acid. The separated material gave colourless flakes of the pyridone acid from alcohol, m. p. 109°. (Found: N, 4.1. C₁₅H₁₉O₈N requires N, 4.1 per cent).

Ethyl 1-(β)-Chloroethyl-2-keto-3-carbethoxy-5-carboxy-1:2-dihydro-pyridine-6-acetate (III, X=X'=CO₂Et; R=CH₂·CH₂Cl; R'=H).—The pyridone (III, X=X'=CO₂Et; R=CH₂·CH₂OH; R'=H; 2 g.) was dissolved in thionyl chloride (5 c.c.) and boiled under reflux (4 hours) till no more hydrogen chloride evolved. After removal of thionyl chloride, the product was poured into ice and crystallised from alcohol, m. p. 115°. (Found: C, 49.73; H, 5.0. C₁₅H₁₈O₇NCl requires C, 50.0; H, 5.0 per cent).

Ethyl-1-Vinyl-2-keto-3-carbethoxy-5-carboxy-1:2-dihydro-pyridine-6-acetate (X=X'=CO₂Et; R=-CH=CH₂; R'=H).—The pyridone (III, X=X'=CO₂Et; R=CH₂·CH₂OH; R'=H; 1 g.) was treated with phosphorus pentabromide (4 g.) under ether (100 c.c.). The mixture was boiled under reflux (2 hours). The alcoholic solution of the material obtained on removal of ether was treated with an aqueous solution of potassium cyanide (2 g.) in water (5 c.c.). The mixture was boiled under reflux (1 hour). The alcohol was removed under reduced pressure and acidified. It was crystallised from alcohol, m. p. 130-33°. (Found: N, 4.3. C₁₅H₁₇O₇N requires N, 4.3 per cent).

Ethyl 3-Cyano-5-carbethoxy-α-pyrone-6-acetate (II, X=CN; X'=CO₂Et).—Ethoxymethylene cyanoacetic ester (8 g.) in alcohol (20 c.c.) was added to ethyl acetonedicarboxylate (10 g.) dissolved in alcohol (40 c.c.) containing sodium (2 g.) and cooled to 0°. The sodium compound, separating on keeping the mixture for 12 hours, was filtered and washed with ethyl alcohol.

The aqueous solution of the precipitate on acidification liberated the pyrone, which furnished colourless needles from alcohol or acetic acid, m. p. 142°. (Found : C, 55.9; H, 4.6; N, 5.1. $C_{13}H_{13}O_3N$ requires C, 55.9; H, 4.6; N, 5.02 per cent).

Ethyl 2-Keto-3-cyano-5-carboxy-1:2-dihydropyridine-6-acetate (III, X = CN; X' = CO₂Et; R = R' = H).—The pyrone (III, X = CN; X' = CO₂Et; 1 g) was dissolved in aqueous ammonia (10 c.c. of 26%) and kept for 12 hours at room temperature (28°). The mixture was diluted and acidified. The material thus precipitated furnished colourless needles from acetic acid, m. p. 260° (decomp). (Found : N, 11.3. $C_{11}H_{10}O_3N_2$ requires N, 11.2 per cent).

Ethyl 1-Ethyl-2-keto-3-cyano-5-carboxy-1:2-dihydropyridine-6-acetate (III, X = CN; X' = CO₂Et; R = Et; R' = H).—The pyrone (II, X = CN; X' = CO₂Et; 1g.) was dissolved in aqueous solution of ethylamine (10 c. c. of 33% solution) and kept for 12 hours at room temperature (28°). The mixture on dilution followed by acidification furnished the desired pyridone which was isolated as colourless needles from acetic acid, m. p. 152°. (Found : N, 9.9. $C_{13}H_{14}O_3N_2$ requires N, 10.0 per cent). *Ethyl 1-Methyl-2-keto-3-cyano-5-carboxy-1:2-dihydropyridine-6-acetate* (III, X = CN; X' = CO₂Et; R = CH₃; R' = H).—The pyrone (II, X = CN; X' = CO₂Et; 1g.) was dissolved in aqueous solution of methylamine (10 c. c. of 30%) and allowed to stand for 12 hours. It was isolated in the usual manner and crystallised from acetic acid, m.p. 210°. (Found : N, 11.0. $C_{12}H_{12}O_3N_2$ requires N, 10.6 per cent).

Ethyl 1-Methyl-2-keto-3-cyano-5-carboxy-1:2-dihydropyridine-6-acetate-methyl ether (III, X = CN; X' = CO₂Et; R = R' = CH₃).—The pyridone (III, X = CN; X' = CO₂Et; R = R' = CH₃; 1.2 g.) was added to a mixture of benzene (200 c.c.) and methyl iodide (10 g.) in which dry silver oxide (5 g.) was suspended. It was boiled under reflux 8 hours and filtered. The material obtained on removal of benzene furnished colourless needles from petroleum ether (b.p. 90-100°), m. p. 123°. (Found : N, 10.05. $C_{12}H_{14}O_3N_2$ requires N, 10.0 per cent).

Methyl Amide of 1-Methyl-2-keto-3-cyano-5-carboxy-1:2-dihydropyridine-6-acetic Acid (III, X = CN; X' = CONHCH₃; R = CH₃; R' = H).—The pyrone (II, X = CN; X' = CO₂Et; 1 g.) was dissolved in aqueous solution of methylamine (40 c.c. of 33%) and kept (12 hours) at room temperature (28°). It was diluted and acidified. It furnished colourless needles from acetic acid, m. p. 285°. (Found : N, 16.7. $C_{11}H_{11}O_4N_3$ requires N, 16.8 per cent).

The condensation of benzaldehyde with the pyridone thus obtained in presence of zinc chloride could not be effected. It gives rose-red colouration with ferric chloride.

Methyl Amide of 1-Methyl-2-keto-3-cayno-5-carboxy-1:2-dihydro-pyridine-6-acetic Acid-ethyl ether (III, X=CN; X'=CONHCH₃; R=CH₃; R'=Et).—The amide mentioned above (0.5 g.) was taken in dry benzene (100 c.c.) containing ethyl bromide (10 c.c.). Dry silver oxide (3 g.) was then suspended and the mixture boiled under reflux for 8 hours. It was then filtered and the residue was washed successively with warm benzene. The precipitate obtained on removal of benzene furnished colourless flakes from the same solvent, m.p. 173°. It does not give colouration with ferric chloride. (Found: N, 14.9. C₁₃H₁₄O₄N₃ requires N, 15.2 per cent).

The amide described in the previous experiment (0.4 g.) was dissolved in dry benzene (100 c.c.) containing emulsified sodium (1 g.). Ethyl formate (5 c.c.) was then added and the mixture was left (8 hours) at the room temperature (28°). Ethyl alcohol (10 c.c.) was then added and the mixture extracted with excess of water. The aqueous solution was shaken several times with ether to remove the last traces of benzene. It was then acidified and the hydroxymethylene derivative thus liberated was dissolved in ether by repeated extraction. The material obtained on removal of ether gave colouration with ferric chloride.

β-Aminopropionic Ester Hydrochloride.—The preparation of the ester from succinimide by the action of sodium hypobromite as described by Van Dorp (*Rec. trav. chim.*, 1891, 10, 4) was not satisfactory. A better yield was however obtained by substituting sodium hypochlorite for hypobromite. Chlorine (5 g.) was passed into water (100 c.c.) containing caustic soda (10 g.) at 0°. Succinimide (5 g.) was added and the mixture vigorously stirred. The solution was kept at 60-70° when evolution of gas commenced with gradual disappearance of the colour. It was acidified with hydrochloric acid and evaporated to dryness. The last traces of water were removed under reduced pressure. The residue (a mixture of sodium chloride and β-aminopropionic acid hydrochloride) was taken in ethyl alcohol (150 c.c.) containing alcoholic hydrochloric acid (10 c.c.). The vapour of alcohol (500 c.c.) was then bubbled through the mixture under reflux (2 hours). The alcoholic solution was filtered and the filtrate evaporated to dryness. The residue was dissolved in minimum quantity of alcohol from which the ester hydrochloride was isolated as glistening flakes, m.p. 58° on addition of benzene, yield 50%. (Found: N, 9.4. C₅H₁₂O₂NCl requires N, 9.1 per cent).

Ethyl 1 (β)-Carbethoxy-ethyl-2-keto-3-cyano-5-carboxy-1 : 2-dihydropyridine-6-acetate (V).—β-Aminopropionic ester hydrochloride (3 g.) was dissolved in alcohol (50 c. c.) and treated with aqueous caustic soda to make it just alkaline. The pyrone (0.5 g.) was added to the mixture which was boiled under reflux for 15 hours). The product obtained on removal of alcohol under reduced pressure was treated with water ; the unchanged pyrone was filtered off ; the aqueous extract after acidification was allowed to stand (1 hour) at the room temperature (28°). The precipitate obtained on filtration was treated with an excess of cold aqueous solution of sodium carbonate and filtered. The insoluble material furnished colourless needles from methyl alcohol, m. p. 113°. (Found: C, 54.7; H, 5.0; N, 8.08. C₁₆H₁₆O₇N₂ requires C, 54.8; H, 5.1; N, 8.0 per cent).

The compound (1 g.) described above was dissolved in dry ether containing ethyl bromide (20 g.). Dry silver oxide (3 g.) was next suspended in the mixture and it was boiled under reflux (8 hours). On removal of ether the ethyl ether was obtained as an oil which did not give any colouration with ferric chloride. It was dissolved in dry ether (25 c. c.) containing ethyl formate (0.5 g.). The mixture was then slowly added to dry ether (25 c. c.) in which emulsified sodium (0.5 g.) was suspended. The mixture was left (8 hours) at the room temperature (28°) and treated with alcohol (1 c. c.). The mixture was extracted with water. The aqueous alkaline solution was acidified and repeatedly extracted with ether. The viscous material which could not be crystallised, obtained on removal of ether, gave with ferric chloride an intense red colouration characteristic of hydroxymethylene acetic esters. The semi-solid mass was then dissolved in ether (10 c. c.) and the mixture boiled under reflux (3 hours) with phosphorus pentoxide (1 g.). The compound was recovered unchanged.

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